

TABLE 2. CONCENTRATION OF SUBSTITUENTS IN SOLUTIONS GIVING RISE TO GRAPH 2

Graph (2)	Solution 0.1016 CoCl ₂
From	510 nm (λ_{max}) 0.497 (O.D.)

Discussion

The graph in Fig. 1 shows how the optical density varies with the wavelength of the light passed through 0.01M sol of cobalt glycinate.

These results show that the predominant electron transfer process is from the anion to the cation, since Ni will more readily be an electron than Co, which conversely shows a greater tendency towards electron release.

The graph on Fig. 2 shows the variation of optical density with wavelength when Co(II) is the cation. Only a very small shift in wavelength occurred between Co and its complexes and in this case the complex absorbed at slightly longer wavelength. Further investigation using cobalt had to be abandoned since even the above mentioned slight shift

in spectrum could not be detected when concentrations were reduced, due mainly to the suppression of complex formation, a result of the necessity of working below pH 7.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Dr. H R. Zaidi, U.G.C. Professor of Chemical Technology, Osmania University for his discussions and helpful guidance in this regard.

References

1. FRANCK and SCHEIBE, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1938, A, 139, 22.
2. RABINOWITCH, *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1942, 14, 112.
3. J. DAINTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 15, 33.
4. L. PAULING, "The Nature of the Chemical Bond", Cornell University Press, New York, 1942, 112.
5. D. P. GRADON, *J. Inorg., Nuclear Chem.*, 1956, 8, 308, Pergamon Press Ltd. London.

3, 5, 5-Trimethyl-1-aryl-2-pyrazolines: Biologically Active Agents

C. J. F. VAZ and V. V. NADKARNY

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory,
St. Xavier's College, Bombay 1.

Manuscript received 22 September 1975,
revised 11 December 1975, accepted 5 January 1976

CHETKOV *et al* have reported that 2-pyrazolines are valuable as corrosion inhibitors¹, and some have been tested for their fungicidal action². But a perusal of available literature does not seem to indicate a further study of the same.

3,5,5-Trimethyl-1-aryl-2-pyrazolines may be easily obtained by the reaction between mesityl oxide and arylhydrazines³. The 1-phenylpyrazoline (I) has been chlorosulphonated⁴ to yield the corresponding 1-(*p*-chlorosulphonylphenyl)-pyrazoline (II) which was

treated with ammonia and amines. The sulphonamides (III) obtained have been investigated for their bactericidal behaviour.

Further the 1-(*p*-nitrophenyl) pyrazoline (IV) was reduced to the amine (V) and its sulphonamide (VI) and phthalimide (VII) derivatives were screened. Mesityl oxide was also condensed with 1-naphthylhydrazine hydrochloride⁶ to give 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(1-naphthyl)-2-pyrazoline (VIII) which is reported here for the first time.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open glass capillaries in a liquid bath.

Preparation of 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(*p*-phenylsulphonamide)-2-pyrazoline (III)

To the sulphonyl chloride (II) (1.0 g, 0.004 mol) was added the amine (1.0 g, excess) in pyridine (5.0 ml) and heated on a steam bath for 1½ to 2 hr. On cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into dilute hydrochloric acid (30 ml) and stirred vigorously. The compound separating out on standing was washed free of acid and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. (Table 1).

TABLE 1. 3, 5, 5-TRIMETHYL-1-(*p*-PHENYLSULPHONAMIDE)-2-PYRAZOLINE (III)

R	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	% S	
			Found	Requires
1. H	118	C ₁₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ SO ₂	11.37	11.99
2. C ₆ H ₅	168	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ N ₃ SO ₂	9.14	9.38
3. C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	139-41	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO ₂	8.73	9.11
4. C ₁₀ H ₇ (1)	214	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO ₂	7.88	8.14

Preparation of 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino)-2-pyrazoline (V):

The freshly prepared nitro compound (IV) (5.0 g) was dissolved in boiling ethanol (60 ml.) and tin foil

was heated under reflux. The solvent was partially removed under vacuum and the mixture poured into excess cold sodium hydroxide (2*N*) solution.

The solid separating out was filtered, washed free from alkali and crystallised from light petroleum. M.P. 156°-8°. Yield 2.4 g. Found: C, 67.43; H, 7.78; N, 24.84. C₁₂H₁₇N₃ requires: C, 67.61; H, 7.98; N, 24.41. ν_{max} 3380, 3250, 1670, 1630, 1530, 1265, 1175 cm⁻¹. N.M.R. spectrum showed signals at 1.1 (6H, s, two -CH₃); 1.90 (3H, s, CH₃ on -C=N); 2.52 (2.1H, d, J = 2Hz); 6.40 to 6.90 (3.85H, m, Ar-H).

Preparation of 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(*p*-benzenesulphonamido-phenyl)-2-pyrazoline (III):

A solution of the sulphonyl chloride⁶ (0.005 mol) dissolved in dry benzene (25 ml.) was added to the amine (V) (2.0 g, 0.01 mol) and the mixture refluxed for 1 hr. On cooling the amine hydrochloride precipitating out was separated by filtration and the amide obtained on evaporation of the filtrate, was recrystallised from ethanol. (Table 2).

Preparation of the *N*-substituted phthalimides (VII):

The amine (V) (1.0 g, 0.005 mol) in glacial acetic acid (7.0 ml.) was added to phthalic anhydride (0.750 g, 0.005 mol) (1.0 g in the case of 3-nitro-phthalic anhydride) in glacial acetic acid (8.0 ml.). The reaction mixture was refluxed on a sand bath for 1-1½ hr. As no compound separated out on cooling, the mixture was poured into water (100 ml) with stirring. The product was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. (Table 2).

Preparation of 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(1-naphthyl)-2-pyrazoline (VIII):

To 1-naphthylhydrazine hydrochloride (4.0 g) in water (15 ml.) was added freshly distilled mesityl oxide (6.0 ml.) in ethanol (20 ml.) and refluxed for 2 hr. The reaction mixture was poured into cold water (150 ml.) when a turbid solution was formed. This was then warmed on a water bath with occasional stirring till it turned clear with a crystalline slurry at the bottom. The product was filtered,

TABLE 2. DERIVATIVES OF 3, 5, 5-TRIMETHYL-1-(*p*-ANILINO)- 2-PYRAZOLINE

Deriv.	Substituent Ar	M.P. °C	Mol. Formula	Found %		Requires %		
				N	S	N	S	
5	VI	C ₆ H ₄ .CH ₃ (<i>p</i>)	178	C ₁₉ H ₂₃ N ₃ SO ₂	11.52	8.93	11.76	8.72
6	VI	C ₆ H ₄ .Br(<i>p</i>)	135	C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₃ BrSO ₂	9.73	7.14	10.02	7.58
7	VI	C ₆ H ₄ .NHAc(<i>p</i>)	229	C ₂₀ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO ₂	15.54	7.69	15.70	8.00
8	VII	H	176	C ₂₀ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂	12.38	—	12.61	—
9	VII	NO ₂	188-9	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₄	14.35	—	14.85	—

(5.0 g) added. Concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 ml) was added over a period of 3 hr. whilst the mixture

washed with water, and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. M.P. 121°. Yield 2.3 g. Found: C,

80.26; H, 7.29; N, 11.91. $C_{16}H_{18}N_2$ requires: C, 80.67; H, 7.56; N, 11.77%.

ν_{max}^{KBr} 1575, 1465, 1370, 813 cm^{-1} , N.M.R. signals at δ 1.11 (6H, s, two $-CH_3$), δ 2.08 (3H, s, CH_3 on $-C=N$), δ 2.75 (2H, d, $J=2Hz$), δ 7.08 to 7.75 (7H, m, Ar-H).

Biological Data

Although 3,5,5-trimethyl-1-(*p*-anilino)-2-pyrazoline (V) has ulcerogenic properties, it also shows good anti-inflammatory action. All the reported compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity against the following microorganisms: *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Salmonella typhosa*, by agar plate technique⁷. Sulphonamides 4 (Table 1) and 6 (Table 2) as well as the 3-nitrophthalimide 9 (Table 2) showed total inhibition whereas sulphonamide 1 (Table 1) showed moderate inhibition⁸.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank Dr. N. J. De Souza, Hoechst Research Centre, Bombay for the spectral data and the pharmacological tests on the amine (V).

References

1. YA B. CHERTKOV, V. N. ZRELOV and V. M. SHECHAGIN, *Chem. Abv.*, 1961, 55, 7819c.
2. G. D. THORN, *Phytopathology*, 1961, 51, 77.
3. K. VON AUWERS and A. KREUDER, *Ber.*, 1925, 58B, 1974.
4. C. J. F. VAZ, M. Sc. Thesis, University of Bombay, 1974.
5. E. FISCHER, *Ann.*, 1886, 232, 237.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Textbook of Practical Organic Chemistry", ELBS, Third Edition.
7. C. H. COLLINS and P. M. LYNE, 'Microbiological Methods', 3rd. Edition, Butterworths, London, 1970, p. 424.
8. R. D'Costa and Z. De Souza (private communication).

Co-ordination complexes of Copper(II), Cobalt(II) and Nickel(II) with N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl/diethyl thiocarbamides

U. K. MURTHY, N. D. JAGNIK and M. G. PARANJPE

University Chemistry Department, Nagpur-10

Manuscript received 1 August 1975,

revised 2 December 1975, accepted 6 December 1975

CO-ORDINATION complexes of metal ions and parent and substituted aryl/alkylthiocarbamides have been reported earlier¹⁻⁴. N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl/diethyl thiocarbamides (I) which have an additional site in their structure for complex formation with metal ions, however, do not appear to have been investigated earlier.

Interaction of certain metal ions *viz.*, Cu^{++} , Co^{++} and Ni^{++} and N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl and diethyl thiocarbamides leading to neutral coloured com-

plexes forms the subject matter of this communication.

It has now been observed that when an aqueous solution of cupric sulphate (0.05M) is added to an alcoholic solution of N-benzoyl-N'-dimethylthiocarbamide (0.1M) at pH 6, a dark green complex, m.p. 205° is formed and can be isolated. On analysis and determination of its composition through complexometric titration by conductometry, the structure IIa was assigned to this complex. This structure is also supported on the basis of its infrared spectrum, where the presence of $\nu(C-S)$ at 727 cm^{-1} and $\nu(Cu-O)^5$ at 535 cm^{-1} bands have been observed. The absence of $-NH$ and $C=O$ stretching frequencies in the infrared spectrum further supported it.

where $R = R' =$ methyl/ethyl.

- where (a) $R = R' =$ methyl and $M =$ copper(II)
 (b) $R = R' =$ ethyl and $M =$ copper(II)
 (c) $R = R' =$ methyl and $M =$ cobalt(II)
 (d) $R = R' =$ ethyl and $M =$ cobalt(II)
 (e) $R = R' =$ methyl and $M =$ nickel(II)
 (f) $R = R' =$ ethyl and $M =$ nickel(II).

The proposed structure II for the complex is in full agreement with structural features of the thiocarbamide in which the hydrogen at position N is likely to contribute more towards enolic ($C-OH$) than thioenolic ($C-SH$) form for the co-valent bond formation in the complex because of the presence of phenyl group at the carbon of the carbonyl group.

When the interaction of Copper (II) was extended to N-benzoyl-N'-diethylthiocarbamide the related complex IIb was obtained. This structure is also supported by the presence of $\nu(C-S)$ at 720 cm^{-1} and $Cu-O$ at 535 cm^{-1} bands and absence of $-NH$ and $C=O$ bands in its infrared spectrum.

Cobalt(II) sulphate and Nickel(II) sulphate and N-benzoyl-N'-dimethyl- and diethyl thiocarbamides also afforded the related cobalt(II), IIc and II d and nickel(II), IIe and II f complexes. The infrared spectra of all these complexes also indicated